

**EXPORT OF AGRICULTURAL AND PROCESSED FOOD PRODUCTS FROM
V.O.CHIDAMBARANAR PORT, TUTICORIN, INDIA – AN ANALYTICAL STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Export development is seen as a determinant of import capacity, which, in turn, is a determinant of the level of household activity. The raise in revenue that comes directly from exports leads in time to a rise in demand for ample range of products and ultimately involves investment in facilities providing such products.

KEY WORDS: APEDA (AGRICULTURAL AND PROCESSED FOOD PRODUCTS), Export , V.O.C. Port.

INTRODUCTION

Export businesses are essential for economic development of any Nation. Apparently it increases foreign exchanges to nation. India as a developing economy our government is concentrating, helping and facilitating export businesses and exporters. Export plays a significant role in a country's growth and development process. The significance of export as one of the contributing factor in the development of any country has long been acknowledged by countless economists. The growth of exports sectors leads to the inflow of foreign direct investment, foreign loans and advance technology. Export activities is developed between the foreign countries which promotes strong political relations among dissimilar economies of the world. Therefore present study is taken on Export of agricultural and processed food products from V.O.Chidambaranar Port .

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Shinoj P et al (2008)¹ examine the relative advantage of India in agricultural export vis-a-vis Asia in the post reform era. From 1991 to 2004, ten major agricultural produce group are measured. India has been able to maintain relative gain in commodities like cashew and oil meals, but tea, coffee, spices, marine goods have been negatively affected. Nageshwara et al (2009)², India is one among the top ten producers in the world for rice, buffalo milk, wheat, cow milk, fresh vegetables, sugar cane, potatoes, groundnut, pepper mint and buffalo meat.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To make out quantity exported from the year 2014- 15 to 2018 -19 from Tuticorin port
2. To know about the value of agricultural and processed food products exported in Tuticorin port from the year 2014 -2015 to 2018 -19
3. To examine the products exported from Tuticorin port individually and totally for the study period
4. To find correlation between quantity exported and vale from 2016- 17 to 2018- 19.
5. To obtain findings based on analysis and make conclusions.

Period of study five years from 2014-15 to 2018-19.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an analytical research, secondary data are collected from the website of Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics (DGCI&S) .

TOOLS OF ANALYSIS

Simple Average, standard deviation, co – efficient of variation are used to do analyses for quantity exported. Correlation is used to study the relationship between quantity exported with its value.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Finding about the quantity exported and its value in rupees is important for the present study. Therefore, analyzed and presented below.

APEDA PRODUCTS EXPORTS

Agricultural and processed goods exported from Tuticorin port from the year 2014 – 2015 to 2018-2019 are presented in below table no 1.

Table 1
INDIA EXPORT OF APEDA PRODUCTS IN TUTICORIN PORT

Sl. No.	Product	Quantity In Quintal					Total	CV
		18-19 yr	17-18 yr	16-17 yr	15-16yr	14-15yr		
1	Poultry Products	4653604.9	3760231	3732278	5388763	4775649	22310525.2	14.24
2	Cucumber and Gherkins(Prepd. & Presvd)	397572.6	425577.4	285170.2	267146.1	332073.5	1707539.75	18.05
3	Floriculture	44727.59	45576.94	47344.95	47949.68	33906.45	219505.61	11.69
4	Fresh Onions	524851.45	392888.6	336120.9	417814.9	350479.5	2022155.23	16.55
5	Other Fresh Vegetables	256482.65	343370.1	329705.9	396322.8	173857.5	1499738.98	25.76
6	Albumin(Eggs & Milk)	13495.5	13633	12258.75	8547.1	3972.5	51906.85	35.58
7	Mango Pulp	37836.63	69372.04	110541.3	96448.52	33924	348122.47	43.94
8	Processed Fruits, Juices & Nuts	139207.32	79334.51	21894.64	15913.99	4872.7	261223.16	96.78
9	Other Fresh Fruits	122529.46	114414.4	161895.5	139628.9	90556.6	629024.86	19.06
10	Cereal Preparations	30389.48	26343.93	22856	21990.24	21022.43	122602.08	14.03
11	Miscellaneous Preparations	50364.48	22282.46	21731.43	21303.14	20771.99	136453.5	42.31
12	Others (Betel Leaves & Nuts)	8853.84	7666.37	7386.41	7818.01	7290.07	39014.7	7.15
13	Processed Vegetables	24005.35	17931.15	24936.09	19509.54	20904.86	107286.99	12.35
14	Other Cereals	46377.17	36441.67	31750.21	26815.71	20619.98	162004.74	26.98
15	Pulses	24680.84	17915.57	32132.09	45296.43	23645.95	143670.88	32.84
16	Jaggery & Confectionery	9499.07	9478.93	6533.77	4958.27	6587.88	37057.92	24.21
17	Milled Products	30925.4	22514.47	13705.52	23933.87	49766.21	140845.47	42.99
18	Groundnuts	5838.93	3084.46	7044.86	10463.4	5297.2	31728.85	38.24
19	Fruits & Vegetables Seeds	805	536.41	3126.55	3294.33	1161.29	8923.58	66.23
20	Dairy Products	1694.14	1213.85	246.13	218.22	1530.07	4902.41	64.28
21	Buffalo Meat		0	280	280		560	70.71
22	Cocoa Products	240.63	45.38	24.18	8.84	20.48	339.51	128.37
23	Wheat	0.25	1325.45	640.04	0.5	0.8	1967.04	134.14
24	Processed Meat	307.46					307.46	0
25	Fresh Mangoes	533.33	183.68	259.5	33.82	336.82	1347.15	61.47
26	Natural Honey	519.23	18.03	47.96	13.01	49.61	647.84	150.81
27	Casein	55			188	194.8	437.8	44.10
28	Alcoholic Beverages	10.63	7.2	20.23	31.41	78.7	148.17	87.52

29	Fresh Grapes	1.8			30		31.8	88.67
30	Guargum		0.5				0.5	0
31	Basmati Rice	1577	340.15	215.05	41.3	83.64	2257.14	126.81
32	Non Basmati Rice	118115.46	246202.3	199507.2	129319.6	573976.1	1267120.62	65.89
33	Walnuts		2				2	0
34	Maize	6133.85	40839.16	59.04	10101	623903.8	681036.85	179.32
	Total	6551236.4	5698771	5409712	7104183	7176534		
	Count	31	31	29	31	29		
	Mean	211330.21	183831.3	186541.8	229167.2	247466.7		
	Stdev	819733.2	663268.5	677441.2	948119.4	871549.3		
	CV	387.89211	360.8028	363.1579	413.7239	352.1885		

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics Annual Export

From the table it is evident that , there are thirty four products are exported from Tuticorin port. Out of which walnuts of two quintal exported only in the 2017 -18. Average score of the quantity exported during the study period are 211330.21, 183831.3, 186541.8, 229167.2 and 247466.7 for the year 2018-19, 2017-18, 2016-17, 2015-16 and 2014-15 respectively. Highest average is identified in the year 2014-15 and second highest standard deviation score than the other three years. Consistency in exports is found in the 2014-15 and an inconsistency export is evidenced in the year 2015-16.

Poultry product is exported more in quantity than other agricultural processed food products. Second highest quantity export is fresh onions. Last three place secured by fresh grapes, walnuts and guargum thought these average score are 31.8, 2 and 0.5.

CORRELATION OF QUANTITY WITH ITS VALUE

Quantity exported with its value of three years from 2016-17 to 2018-19 is presented in the below table. Researcher analysed relationship of quantity and value of three years and give in Table no 2.

Table 2
Relationship of quantity and value of goods exported

Sl. No.	Product	18-19 yr		17-18		16-17	
		Quantity in quintal	Rs in Crore	Quantity in quintal	Rs in Crore	Quantity in quintal	Rs in Crore
1	Poultry Products	4653604.9	373.94	3760231	281.78	3732278	269.23
2	Cucumber and Gherkins(Prepd. & Presvd)	397572.6	262.15	425577.4	263.3	285170.2	161.99
3	Floriculture	44727.59	124.11	45576.94	109.52	47344.95	117.72
4	Fresh Onions	524851.45	104.34	392888.6	143.7	336120.9	57.07
5	Other Fresh Vegetables	256482.65	77.81	343370.1	104.05	329705.9	88.45
6	Albumin(Eggs & Milk)	13495.5	63.14	13633	52.45	12258.75	59.54
7	Mango Pulp	37836.63	16.15	69372.04	33.68	110541.3	55.53
8	Processed Fruits, Juices & Nuts	139207.32	78.75	79334.51	48.04	21894.64	19.39
9	Other Fresh Fruits	122529.46	44.58	114414.4	41.03	161895.5	55.56
10	Cereal Preparations	30389.48	38.85	26343.93	33.99	22856	35.03
11	Miscellaneous Preparations	50364.48	32.14	22282.46	28.56	21731.43	23.39
12	Others (Betel Leaves & Nuts)	8853.84	26.51	7666.37	21.06	7386.41	20.67
13	Processed Vegetables	24005.35	26.22	17931.15	18.2	24936.09	21.5

14	Other Cereals	46377.17	14.65	36441.67	11.87	31750.21	9.39
15	Pulses	24680.84	14.24	17915.57	8.21	32132.09	15.94
16	Jaggery & Confectionery	9499.07	9.87	9478.93	10.29	6533.77	8.16
17	Milled Products	30925.4	10.4	22514.47	7.38	13705.52	4.34
18	Groundnuts	5838.93	4.67	3084.46	2.44	7044.86	6.12
19	Fruits & Vegetables Seeds	805	4.93	536.41	3.27	3126.55	4.22
20	Dairy Products	1694.14	9.55	1213.85	5.81	246.13	0.92
21	Buffalo Meat			0	0	280	0.32
22	Cocoa Products	240.63	0.47	45.38	0.54	24.18	0.23
23	Wheat	0.25	0	1325.45	0.31	640.04	0.15
24	Processed Meat	307.46	0.59				
25	Fresh Mangoes	533.33	0.56	183.68	0.15	259.5	0.23
26	Natural Honey	519.23	1.27	18.03	0.06	47.96	0.1
27	Casein	55	0.11				
28	Alcoholic Beverages	10.63	0.01	7.2	0.02	20.23	0.03
29	Fresh Grapes	1.8	0.01				
30	Guargum			0.5	0		
31	Basmati Rice	1577	0.94	340.15	0.29	215.05	0.15
32	Non Basmati Rice	118115.46	51.33	246202.3	86.07	199507.2	74.02
33	Walnuts			2	0.01		
34	Maize	6133.85	0.81	40839.16	6.1	59.04	0.02
	Total	6551236.4	1393.1	5698771	1322.18	5409712	1109.41
	r	0.816941		0.731849		0.808146	

Source: Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics Annual Export

Above table shows positive relationship between quantity exported and its value in V.o. chidambaranar port and its result are 0.81 in the year 2018 – 19, 0.73 in 2017 -18 and 0.8 in the year 2016 -17. Chart 1,2 and 3 explains the positive relationship of quantity and value of goods exported.

Chart 1

Relationship in the year 2018 -19

Source: Table 2 quantity and value for the year 2018 -19

Chart 2
Relationship in the year 2017 -18

Source: Table 2 quantity and value for the year 2017 -18

Chart 3
Relationship in the year 2016 -17

Source: Table 2 quantity and value for the year 2016 -17

FINDING OF THE STUDY

Average score of the quantity exported during the study period are 211330.21, 183831.3, 186541.8, 229167.2 and 247466.7 for the year 2018-19, 2017-18, 2016-17, 2015-16 and 2014-15 respectively. Poultry product is exported more in quantity than other agricultural processed food products. Second highest quantity export is fresh onions. Last three place secured by fresh grapes, walnuts and guargum though these average score are 31.8, 2 and 0.5. positive relationship between quantity exported and its value in V.o. chidambaranar port and its result are 0.81 in the year 2018 – 19, 0.73 in 2017 -18 and 0.8 in the year 2016 -17.

CONCLUSION

Indian agricultural and processed food exports have a significant share in country’s total exports. Therefore, Government has to take steps to boost it more and it is evidenced by our finance minister Mrs. Nirmala Sitharaman

statement as she said a comprehensive Agriculture Export Policy was launched on December 6, 2018 with the plan to double farmers' income by 2022. Additionally, Transport and Marketing Assistance (TMA) scheme launched on March 5, 2019 for the mitigating difficulties of a higher cost of transportation for export of specified Agricultural products.

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